

KETIDAKPASTIAN HASIL PENGUKURAN

Ketelitian, ketidakpastian hasil pengukuran

Ketelitian, ketidakpastian hasil pengukuran

Resolusi

Resolusi

Kalibrasi

Ketepatan (Pengukuran berulang)

$$\text{Ketepatan} = 1 - |\Delta x|/x$$

Pengukuran ke-	Hasil pengukuran (cm)
1	2.9 ± 0.025
2	2.95 ± 0.025
3	2.9 ± 0.025
4	3 ± 0.025
5	2.95 ± 0.025

Kalibrasi

Kalibrasi

Kalibrasi

A

B

C

D

E

Kalibrasi

- A 1 cm
- B 2 cm
- C 3 cm
- D 4 cm
- E 5 cm

Panjang asli (cm)	Hasil Pengukuran (cm)	Penyimpangan (cm)
1	1 ± 0.05	0
2	1.9 ± 0.05	-0.1
3	2.9 ± 0.05	-0.1
4	4 ± 0.05	0
5	5 ± 0.05	0

Ketepatan (Pengukuran berulang)

PRECISION VS ACCURACY

✓ Precision
✗ Accuracy

✗ Precision
✓ Accuracy

✗ Precision
✗ Accuracy

✓ Precision
✓ Accuracy

Melaporkan/menuliskan hasil pengukuran

$$x = (x_{\text{terbaik}} \pm \Delta x) \text{ satuan}$$

$$x = (\bar{x} \text{ satuan} \pm \frac{\Delta x}{\bar{x}} \cdot 100\%)$$

Contoh:

1.965 ± 0.06 Hz, 1.965 ± 3.0% Hz

20.0 ± 0.5 cm, 20 ± 2.5% cm

220.0 ± 0.5 mm, 220 ± 0.2% mm,

50.0 ± 0.01 g, 50 ± 0.02% g

Melaporkan/menuliskan hasil pengukuran

$$x = (x_{\text{terbaik}} \pm \Delta x) \text{ satuan}$$

Penulisan hasil pengukuran:

- Ketelitian 0.1%, penulisan 3 angka di belakang koma
- Ketelitian 1.0%, penulisan 2 angka di belakang koma
- Ketelitian 10%, penulisan 1 angka di belakang koma

$$1.9 \pm 0.06 \text{ Hz}, 1.9 \pm 3.0\% \text{ Hz}$$

$$20.5 \pm 0.5 \text{ cm}, 20.5 \pm 2.5\% \text{ cm}$$

$$220.10 \pm 0.5 \text{ mm}, 220.10 \pm 0.2\% \text{ mm},$$

$$50.143 \pm 0.01 \text{ g}, 50.143 \pm 0.02\% \text{ g}$$

Melaporkan/menuliskan hasil pengukuran

$$x = (x_{\text{terbaik}} \pm \Delta x) \text{ satuan}$$

Pembulatan harga,

- > 0.5 dinaikan ke atas, contoh: 12.78 \rightarrow 12.8
- < 0.5 diturunkan ke bawah, contoh: 12.45 \rightarrow 12.4
- $= 0.5$, ganjil dinaikkan ke atas, contoh: 12.75 \rightarrow 12.8
- $= 0.5$, genap tetap, contoh: 12.65 \rightarrow 12.6

Melaporkan/menuliskan hasil pengukuran

$$x = (x_{\text{terbaik}} \pm \Delta x) \text{ satuan}$$

Ketidakpastian (uncertainty) pengukuran tunggal,

$\Delta x = \frac{1}{2}$ skala resolusi (skala terkecil

$\Delta x = 0.5 \text{ mm}$ (mistar, skala terkecil 1 mm)

$\Delta x = 0.5 \text{ gram}$ (timbangan, skala terkecil 1 gram)

$\Delta x = 0.005 \text{ mm}$ (dial indicator, skala terkecil 0.01 mm)

$\Delta x = 0.05 \text{ mm}$ (jangka sorong, 0.1 mm)

Melaporkan/menuliskan hasil pengukuran

$$x = (x_{\text{terbaik}} \pm \Delta x) \text{ satuan}$$

Ketidakpastian (uncertainty) pengukuran berulang,

$$\bar{x} \pm z S_x$$

$$\bar{x} \pm t_{v,95} \frac{S_x}{\sqrt{n}}$$

Table 4.4 Student's *t* Distribution

<i>v</i>	<i>t</i> ₅₀	<i>t</i> ₉₀	<i>t</i> ₉₅	<i>t</i> ₉₉
1	1.000	6.314	12.706	63.657
2	0.816	2.920	4.303	9.925
3	0.765	2.353	3.182	5.841
4	0.741	2.132	2.770	4.604
5	0.727	2.015	2.571	4.032
6	0.718	1.943	2.447	3.707
7	0.711	1.895	2.365	3.499
8	0.706	1.860	2.306	3.355
9	0.703	1.833	2.262	3.250
10	0.700	1.812	2.228	3.169
11	0.697	1.796	2.201	3.106
12	0.695	1.782	2.179	3.055
13	0.694	1.771	2.160	3.012
14	0.692	1.761	2.145	2.977
15	0.691	1.753	2.131	2.947
16	0.690	1.746	2.120	2.921
17	0.689	1.740	2.110	2.898
18	0.688	1.734	2.101	2.878
19	0.688	1.729	2.093	2.861
20	0.687	1.725	2.086	2.845
21	0.686	1.721	2.080	2.831
30	0.683	1.697	2.042	2.750
40	0.681	1.684	2.021	2.704
50	0.680	1.679	2.010	2.679
60	0.679	1.671	2.000	2.660
∞	0.674	1.645	1.960	2.576

$$\bar{x} \pm t_{v,95} \frac{S_x}{\sqrt{n}}$$

Misal:

- Jumlah pengukuran 10x, Standar Deviasi, $S_x = 0.8657$, dari tabel pada $v = 10 - 1 = 9$ dan t_{95} , diperoleh harga 2.262, maka harga ketidakpastiannya adalah

$$\Delta x = 2.262 \times 0.8657 / (10)^{1/2} = 0.619$$

- Menggunakan excel = $TINV(0.05,v) = 2.228$, dimana $v = 10$, tingkat kepercayaan 95%.

Melaporkan/menuliskan hasil pengukuran

$$x = (x_{\text{terbaik}} \pm \Delta x) \text{ satuan}$$

$Y = (x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_n)$, $x = \text{variabel ukur}$
Ketelitian x , ($u_1, u_2, u_3, \dots, u_n$)

Ketelitian y ,

$$u_y = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial y}{\partial x_1} u_1\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial y}{\partial x_2} u_2\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial y}{\partial x_3} u_3\right)^2 + \dots + \left(\frac{\partial y}{\partial x_n} u_n\right)^2}$$

Contoh-1

Misalkan $y = Ax_1 + Bx_2$

Besar ketelitian y ,

$$u_y = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial y}{\partial x_1} u_1\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial y}{\partial x_2} u_2\right)^2}$$

Diperoleh,

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\partial y}{\partial x_1} &= A \\ \frac{\partial y}{\partial x_2} &= B\end{aligned}$$

$$u_y = \sqrt{(Au_1)^2 + (Bu_2)^2}$$

$$u_y = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial y}{\partial x_1} u_1\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial y}{\partial x_2} u_2\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial y}{\partial x_3} u_3\right)^2 + \dots + \left(\frac{\partial y}{\partial x_n} u_n\right)^2}$$

Contoh-2

Misalkan $F=ma$

$m=10\pm0.01$ kg dan $a=5\pm0.01$ m/s²

Besar ketelitian F ,

$$u_F = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial F}{\partial m} u_1\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial F}{\partial a} u_2\right)^2}$$

Diperoleh,

$$\frac{\partial F}{\partial m} = a = 5 \frac{m}{s^2}$$

$$\frac{\partial F}{\partial a} = m = 10 \text{ kg}$$

$$u_F = \sqrt{(au_1)^2 + (mu_2)^2}$$

$$u_F = \sqrt{(5 \times 0.05)^2 + (10 \times 0.01)^2}$$

$$u_F = \sqrt{(0.25)^2 + (0.1)^2}$$

$$u_F = \sqrt{(0.0625) + (0.01)}$$

$$u_F = \sqrt{(0.0625) + (0.01)} = \sqrt{0.0725} = 0.27$$

Jadi, $F=50\pm0.27$ N (0,54%)

Contoh-3

Misalkan $A = P.L$

$L = 1000 \pm 0.5$ mm, dan $P = 500 \pm 0.5$ mm

Besar ketelitian A,

$$u_F = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial A}{\partial L} u_P\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial A}{\partial P} u_L\right)^2}$$

Diperoleh,

$$\frac{\partial A}{\partial L} = P = 500 \text{ mm}$$

$$\frac{\partial A}{\partial P} = L = 1000 \text{ mm}$$

$$u_A = \sqrt{(Lu_L)^2 + (Pu_P)^2}$$

$$u_A = \sqrt{(1000 \times 0.5)^2 + (500 \times 0.5)^2}$$

$$u_A = \sqrt{(500)^2 + (250)^2}$$

$$u_A = \sqrt{(250.000) + (62.500)}$$

$$u_A = \sqrt{312.500} = 559.017 \text{ mm}$$

Jadi, $A = 500.000 \pm 559$ mm (0,11%)

Table 4.8 Measured Force Data for Exercise Problems

F (N) Set 1	F (N) Set 2	F (N) Set 3
51.9	51.9	51.1
51.0	48.7	50.1
50.3	51.1	51.4
49.6	51.7	50.5
51.0	49.9	49.7
50.0	48.8	51.6
48.9	52.5	51.0
50.5	51.7	49.5
50.9	51.3	52.4
52.4	52.6	49.5
51.3	49.4	51.6
50.7	50.3	49.4
52.0	50.3	50.8
49.4	50.2	50.8
49.7	50.9	50.2
50.5	52.1	50.1
50.7	49.3	52.3
49.4	50.7	48.9
49.9	50.5	50.4
49.2	49.7	51.5

Table 4.1 Sample of Random Variable x

i	x_i	i	x_i
1	0.98	11	1.02
2	1.07	12	1.26
3	0.86	13	1.08
4	1.16	14	1.02
5	0.96	15	0.94
6	0.68	16	1.11
7	1.34	17	0.99
8	1.04	18	0.78
9	1.21	19	1.06
10	0.86	20	0.96

The density of air is to be determined by measuring its pressure and temperature for insertion in the ideal-gas equation of state; that is,

$$p = \rho RT$$

The value of R for air is 287.1 J/kg-K and may be assumed exact for this calculation. The temperature and pressure are measured as

$$T = 55 \pm 0.4^\circ\text{C}$$

$$p = 125 \pm 0.5 \text{ kPa}$$

Determine the nominal value for the density in kg/m^3 and its uncertainty.

In a student laboratory experiment a measurement is made of a certain resistance by different students. The values obtained were:

Reading	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
Resistance, $k\Omega$	12.0	12.1	12.5	11.8	13.6	11.9	12.2	11.9	12.0	12.3	12.1	11.85

TERIMA KASIH